

Adherence to Brain Trauma Foundation Guidelines for Intracranial Pressure Monitoring and Cerebrospinal Fluid Drainage

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Background

Traumatic brain injury (TBI) is the 3rd leading cause of injury-related deaths in the US

Direct and indirect costs of TBI amount to \$7.6B per year

The Brain Trauma Foundation (BTF) established guidelines in managing severe TBI, but median adherence rate is only 60.7%

TBI adherence rates < 65% were associated with a two-fold increase in inpatient hospital mortality

Adoption of BTF guidelines resulted in a drop of 24-hour mortality rate by 59%

Purpose

To increase adherence to BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage during the first 24 hours after intensive care unit (ICU) admission of adults with severe TBI and external ventricular drain (EVD)

Objectives

- Describe baseline adherence rates to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage
- Adopt or develop evidence-based algorithms/protocols on ICP monitoring and CSF drainage
- Develop an educational program on the evidence-based ICP-monitoring algorithm and CSF drainage protocol
- Implement the Seattle International Traumatic Brain Injury Consensus Conference (SIBICC) algorithm and CSF drainage protocol
- Evaluate adherence rates to the BTF guidelines for ICP monitoring and CSF drainage after implementation

Methods

Evidence-Based Practice Project

Convenience Sample of 12 patients (6 pre- and 6 post-implementation)

Inclusion Criteria:

- 18 years of age and older
- Severe TBI diagnosis
- Admission to the surgical ICU
- Abnormal CT or normal CT with at least 2 of the following conditions:
 - Age over 40 years
 - Unilateral or bilateral posturing
 - Systolic blood pressure < 90 mm Hg
- EVD in place

Exclusion: Brain death within 24 hours of Emergency Department admission

Setting: Harbor-UCLA Medical Center (Level 1 Trauma Center)

Protocol development using Delphi method

Pre/Post evaluation of compliance to protocol guidelines

CSF Drainage Protocol

ICP (mm Hg)	CSF Drainage Method	When to Monitor and Document ICP and CPP
21-29	Intermittent	Pre-drain, post-drain, and end of hour
≥ 30 or ≥ 3 consecutive drains within an hour	Continuous	End of hour

For intermittent CSF drainage:

- Open the EVD until CSF stops to drain
- Record ICP and CPP immediately after CSF drainage when the ICP reading stabilizes and stops fluctuating
- If 3 or more consecutive intermittent drainage is required within 1 hour, open the EVD to continuous CSF drainage

Do not exceed maximum CSF drainage of 25 mL/hour

Measures

Completeness of ICP Monitoring

$$\frac{\text{Number of ICP readings}}{\text{Total number required ICP readings per protocol}}$$

ICP Monitoring Adherence Rate

$$\frac{\text{Number of patients with complete data}}{\text{Total number of patients with ICP monitoring}}$$

Completeness of CSF Drainage

$$\frac{\text{Number of CSF drainage events}}{\text{Total number of required CSF drainage events per protocol}}$$

CSF Drainage Adherence Rate:

$$\frac{\text{Number of patients with complete data}}{\text{Total number of patients with ICP monitoring}}$$

Expected Results

Future Implications for Practice

Decreased variation in practice

Future research on effects to improve outcomes of adult patients with severe TBI

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